

Extended Brief Policy Report in Spain: Light Pollution

By Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel

What this problem entails, its scope in our country compared to other countries, and how this problem will evolve if no action is taken.

Light pollution is defined as the “alteration of the natural light levels” in the atmosphere (but can also interfere with water or any other medium) where there are environmental impacts (including human health impacts) or impairments or interferences with amenities and other legitimate uses of the environment. This definition is a consequence of the definition of air pollutants in the “1979 Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution” and was explicitly discussed in the UN Report of the International Law Commission on the work of its sixty-seventh session[000].

The problem of defining light pollution has been part of the issue, as it has inconsistent definitions across different regulations. For example, the “Ley 34/2007, de 15 de noviembre, de calidad del aire y protección de la atmósfera” has the same air pollution definition as [A] (Art.3 e), which naturally includes light pollution, but includes a specific definition of light pollution in Art. 3. f) that contradicts Art. 3 e) because it includes the usefulness of the light in the definition. This is contradictory because it suggests that 100% useful lights would not disturb ecosystems or harm human health. This kind of mismatch between the UN definition of light pollution and national definitions exists mainly due to the influence of the lighting industry lobby and can be found even in EU documents [00].

In general, the environmental impacts [0] of light pollution are transversal across all species, as species use the day-night cycle to regulate their hormonal cycles, rest, or navigate, and the presence of light at night interferes with those services, becoming a physical barrier for many species. At the same time, light at night is extremely useful for nighttime activities and providing a sense of safety and security.

Spain had the highest rates of light pollution per capita and per street light in the EU until 2012 [1-5]. After 2012, due to the limitations of satellite data [6], lack of national statistics, and incorrect estimates by IDAE [7] and statistics from Ministerio de Industria y Comercio [8][9], where the statistics changed by 83% from 2006 to 2007 due to a change in the C.N.A.E., it is not possible to have accurate data on energy consumption or light emissions from 2012 until 2021. The best estimations currently available are expected to be stable until 2017 [10-11]. From 2021 until today, there is data under analysis using the SDGSAT-1 data and new data is expected to come from the period 2010 until 2024 from the calibration of the data from the International Space Station (ISS). It is not uncommon to find estimations of light emissions that do not consider the limitations of the satellites [BC].

Globally, it is known that light pollution is growing at a rate between 2.2% [12] and 10% [13], with a minimum increase of 49% between 1992 and 2017 [14]. However, these data are known to be only lower estimates due to satellite data limitations, and real values can be up to 400%

higher in the blue light content estimated with the most used datasets. This uncertainty can be solved by using alternative data such as the mentioned SDGSAT-1 and ISS data.

A large part of this uncertainty is due to the transition from discharge lamp technology, mainly High-pressure sodium lamps (traditional orange street lights), to new technology, LEDs. LEDs are a very controversial technology for outdoor lighting (not for indoor) because of their promised energy efficiency [15] and performances that have been questioned even by the Comité Español de Iluminación [16] and the Joint Research Center [17]. This is considered in policy documents as an expected outcome of the LEDs [18], although this effect was already forecasted on several occasions from 2004 to 2014 and by Bellond [19-21].

Currently, a large part of the infrastructure has been replaced by LEDs, which has caused problems in several municipalities due to low quality [22], although there are no public estimates of the impact of this problem. To address this issue, the IDAE issued a list of non-binding recommendations [23]. Another significant problem is the rebound effect from cheap light sources [13] and the increased blue emissions of the most popular LEDs [14,19]. Another issue is the lack of Life Cycle Cost analysis of new lighting installations, including the manufacturing of LEDs and their light pollution impacts [24].

If no actions are taken, light emissions can increase indefinitely, disturbing essential ecological services like pollinators, and large amounts of public funds will be spent on obsolete technologies, leading to a waste of resources and increased CO2 emissions.

What are the main scientific consensuses and disagreements regarding the causes and consequences of this problem.

In general, there is a consensus that the main reasons for the source of light pollution are: the usefulness of the pollutant, lack of awareness of its consequences on the environment and health, fear of darkness, use for status purposes and advertising, and lack of enforcement.

There is a large consensus on the environmental impacts of light pollution. There is a consensus that light can produce a sense of safety [VB], but in general, research shows that if there are any real impacts in the developed world, they are small. Most well-designed research shows no impacts or even negative impacts. The scientific community requests that a monitoring scheme be established to control light pollution [AB]. Another problem is the lack of scientific basis for current lighting standards [SD].

There is still discussion on some potential health impacts of light as a factor that could increase the risk of some diseases like cancer, diabetes, heart disease, and obesity. Although extreme cases of circadian disruption are recognized by the WHO as carcinogenic type 2A (probably carcinogenic to humans). Other impacts on humans like glare or the promotion of vectors like mosquitoes are well established.

What we know about the instruments and public policy measures that have worked in other countries or could work to solve this problem.

There is limited evidence of regulations that effectively control light pollution. Only the La Palma and north of Tenerife law has proven to be effective against light pollution [2]. Also, the French law and some Italian laws [25] have explored limits on total emissions and percentages of blue lights emitted [26]. There are other approaches, although some ignore the nature of light pollution [27]. The promotion of good practices, which has been done recently by IDAE, such as the use of LEDs with no blue light emission [28], and the generalized use of environmental impact assessments, would also be solutions [29]. According to this last law, almost all installations should pass an environmental impact assessment because nearly all occasions impact a Natura 2000 reserve directly or indirectly.

List of Sources:

[000]https://legal.un.org/ilc/documentation/english/summary_records/a_cn4_sr3260.pdf

[00] European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment, Light pollution – Mitigation measures for environmental protection, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/906521>

[0] Gaston, Kevin J., and Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel. "Environmental impacts of artificial light at night." *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 47.1 (2022): 373-398.

[1] Sánchez de Miguel, A., Zamorano Calvo, J., Mosquera de Arancibia, A., & Almazán González, M. (2011). El alumbrado público español, el mayor gasto eléctrico por habitante en Europa.

[2] Sánchez de Miguel, A. (2015). Variación espacial, temporal y espectral de la contaminación lumínica y sus fuentes: Metodología y resultados (Versión 1) [Familia Sánchez de Miguel]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1422725>

[3] Sánchez de Miguel, A., & Benayas Polo, R. (2019). Ranking de la Contaminación lumínica en España 2015. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2616957>

[4] Sánchez de Miguel, A., & Martín-Ruiz, S. (2021). Gasto en alumbrado público y la contaminación lumínica asociada en España y Andalucía (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5524240>

[5] Sánchez de Miguel, A., Zamorano, J., Castaño, J. G., & Pascual, S. (2014). Evolution of the energy consumed by street lighting in Spain estimated with DMSP-OLS data. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 139, 109-117.

[6] Linares Arroyo, H., Abascal, A., Degen, T., Aubé, M., Espey, B. R., Gyuk, G., ... & Kyba, C. C. (2024). Monitoring, trends and impacts of light pollution. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 1-14.

[7] Sánchez de Vera Quintero (2014) V1, Consumo de energía y potencial de ahorro del alumbrado exterior municipal en España.

[8] Estadística de la industria de la Energía Eléctrica 2006, ISBN: 978-84-96275-71-3.

[9] Estadística de la industria de la Energía Eléctrica 2007, ISBN: 978-84-96275-84-3, 1ª Ed. /70/0509.

[10]

Malón, S., de Miguel, A., & Dorremochea, C. (2022). La luz de la razón: la normativa de alumbrado y el futuro de la contaminación lumínica en España. *Astronomía*, 273, 32-37.

[11] Sánchez de Miguel, A., Bennie, J., Rosenfeld, E., Dzurjak, S., & Gaston, K. J. (2022). Environmental risks from artificial nighttime lighting widespread and increasing across Europe. *Science Advances*, 8(37), eabl6891.

[12] Kyba, C. C., Kuester, T., Sánchez de Miguel, A., Baugh, K., Jechow, A., Hölker, F., ... & Guanter, L. (2017). Artificially lit surface of Earth at night increasing in radiance and extent. *Science advances*, 3(11), e1701528.

[13] Kyba, Christopher CM, et al. "Citizen scientists report global rapid reductions in the visibility of stars from 2011 to 2022." *Science* 379.6629 (2023): 265-268.

[14] Sánchez de Miguel, A., Bennie, J., Rosenfeld, E., Dzurjak, S., & Gaston, K. J. (2021). First estimation of global trends in nocturnal power emissions reveals acceleration of light pollution. *Remote Sensing*, 13(16), 3311.

[15] Sánchez de Miguel, A. (2024). Energy efficiency on Philips Lighting products for outdoor lighting [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841609>

[16] Comité Español de Iluminación, (2017). Posibles riesgos de la iluminación LED. ILUMINACION_correcciones3mayo. indd (ceisp. com)(25 noviembre 2020).

[17] Donatello, S., Rodríguez, R., Quintero, M. G. C., JRC, O. W., Van Tichelen, P., Van, V., & Hoof, T. G. V. (2019). Revision of the EU green public procurement criteria for road lighting and traffic signals. Publications Office of the European Union: Luxembourg, 127.

[18] Zissis, G., & Bertoldi, P. (2023). Update on Status of Solid-State Lighting & Smart Lighting Systems.

[19] Sánchez de Miguel, A. La iluminación led: un arma de doble filo. *Tribuna de Astronomía: Revista de astronomía, astrofísica y ciencias del espacio*. 2004(55):70-1.

[20] Luginbuhl, C. B., Boley, P. A., & Davis, D. R. (2014). The impact of light source spectral power distribution on sky glow. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 139, 21-26.

[21] Aubé, M., Roby, J., & Kocifaj, M. (2013). Evaluating potential spectral impacts of various artificial lights on melatonin suppression, photosynthesis, and star visibility. *PLoS one*, 8(7), e67798.

[22] Toledo, C. (2020, septiembre 19). *Valencia inyecta un millón de euros para sustituir las farolas LED defectuosas que Barberá 'compró' a Rus*. *El Mundo*.
<https://www.elmundo.es/comunidad-valenciana/2020/09/19/5f65a572fc6c83754c8b45d7.html>

[23] IDAE. (2022, diciembre). Requerimientos técnicos exigibles para las instalaciones de alumbrado exterior (Versión 1.3). Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía.
https://www.idae.es/sites/default/files/documentos/idae/tecnologias/ahorro_y_eficiencia_energetica/alumbrado_exterior/RequerimientosTecnicosExigibles_v13_Dic2022.pdf

[24] Sánchez de Miguel, A. (2022). The lighting system's Life Cycle Cost including light pollution and manufacturing CO2 emissions (beta) (2.14 (beta)). *Zenodo*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6537166>

[25] Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic. (2022). Light pollution reduction measures in Europe. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12676720>

[26] Bará, Salvador, et al. "Keeping light pollution at bay: a red-lines, target values, top-down approach." *Environmental Challenges* 5 (2021): 100212.

[27] Morgan-Taylor, M. (2023). Regulating light pollution: more than just the night sky. *Science*, 380(6650), 1118-1120.

[AB] Yakushina, Y., Smith, D., & Sánchez de Miguel, A. (2024). Manifesto for Tackling Light Pollution & Proposing EU Light Pollution Monitoring. Meeting on Light Pollution: Challenges and Responses for Monitoring it, Granada, Spain. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12606631>

[BC] Widmer, K., Beloconi, A., Marnane, I., & Vounatsou, P. (2022). Review and assessment of available information on light pollution in Europe. *Elonet Report-ETC HE*, 8.

[28] Agencia Estatal Boletín Oficial del Estado. (2023, abril 21). *Real Decreto 284/2023, de 18 de abril, por el que se establecen las condiciones básicas de accesibilidad y no discriminación

para el acceso y utilización de los espacios públicos urbanizados* (BOE-A-2023-9753). Boletín Oficial del Estado. <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2023/04/21/pdfs/BOE-A-2023-9753.pdf>

[29] Agencia Estatal Boletín Oficial del Estado. (2013, diciembre 9). Ley 21/2013, de 9 de diciembre, de evaluación ambiental (BOE-A-2013-12913). Boletín Oficial del Estado. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2013/BOE-A-2013-12913-consolidado.pdf>

[VB] Peña-García, A., Hurtado, A., & Aguilar-Luzón, M. C. (2015). Impact of public lighting on pedestrians' perception of safety and well-being. *Safety science*, 78, 142-148.

[SD] Fotios, S., & Gibbons, R. (2018). Road lighting research for drivers and pedestrians: The basis of luminance and illuminance recommendations. *Lighting Research & Technology*, 50(1), 154-186.